

SCIENCE LABORATORY ASSESSMENT: BASIS FOR AN ACTION PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses the inventory, handling practices, and management of the Science Laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus. It aims to evaluate the availability and condition of lab equipment, safety handling practices, and management strategies in place. The research methodology involves conducting an inventory assessment of lab equipment, categorizing items into safety-related common equipment, basic apparatus, measuring glassware, non-measuring glassware, and heating equipment. This assessment will provide insights into the adequacy and functionality of the equipment. Additionally, the study will evaluate handling practices concerning personal protective equipment, emergency equipment availability, and laboratory housekeeping standards. This evaluation aims to identify areas for improvement to ensure a safe laboratory environment. The research will also examine management practices, including equipment calibration and repair, inspection of new and used equipment, and the organization of lab spaces. This will help assess the effectiveness of current management practices and highlight areas for enhancement. The findings will inform an Action Plan aimed at improving the Science Laboratory's inventory, safety measures, and management practices, ultimately contributing to enhanced functionality, safety, and efficiency in the laboratory.

Keywords: *science laboratory, safety measures, handling practices, inventory, assessment*

INTRODUCTION

This study focuses on conducting a comprehensive assessment of the science laboratories at Mindoro State University (MinSU) Bongabong Campus, specifically analyzing the variables of science laboratory inventory, handling practices, and management practices. The aim is to evaluate the current state of these variables within the laboratories at the campus, including the availability and adequacy of lab equipment, the efficiency of the handling process, as well as the effectiveness of the managing process. The assessment will provide valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of these variables, identifying areas that require improvement or enhancement within the specific context of MinSU Bongabong Campus. The findings will then be used as a basis for formulating and implementing an Action Plan, tailored to address the identified areas of improvement and enhance the overall functionality and productivity of the science laboratories at MinSU Bongabong Campus. The Action Plan will serve as a map to improve the science laboratory of MinSU Bongabong Campus.

Science educators have suggested that using laboratory activities has numerous educational advantages, and the laboratory has been given a central and distinctive role in science education (Konstam et al., 2018). The statement highlights the educational benefits of laboratory activities in science instruction and acknowledges the laboratory's central and unique role in fostering effective learning experiences. By integrating laboratory activities into science instruction, educators can improve students' understanding, critical thinking skills, inquiry abilities, collaboration, and motivation in science.

Science laboratory is a place for conducting experiments and practicum activities. Students will better understand the subject matter if they are actively involved in the learning process. Laboratory works increase learning motivation of students. Laboratory practices play a vital role to reach out the gap between theory and practice (Cullin et al., 2017). Laboratory applications have been stated to help students define the concepts of science in a more comprehensive and meaningful manner (Harman et al., 2016). Laboratories have long been regarded as an important component in science education (Kwok, 2015). The main purpose of teaching science is to develop the skills of learners, mainly to adapt the dynamic world. The teacher has a great role to reach out this purpose. Science laboratory influence the quality of education and the learning implementation of the teachers and the activities of the students inside the classroom particularly in science. Therefore, the immediate action for updating and improving the science laboratory must be emphasized.

Conducting a science laboratory needs assessment will help the school gain a deeper understanding on science laboratory, prioritize its resources, appeal to stakeholders for donors, and activate linkages with other related agencies.

A science laboratory needs assessment will help to learn about the inventory, handling of material and equipment, and management practices in the laboratory. The

assessment can reveal both a laboratory most pressing needs and leverageable resources so that university can direct funding and resources to produce a well-equipped and knowledgeable student. Nonprofit organizations and related agencies must often make the case for their programs to garner support. A science laboratory needs assessment report, signals that their services and decisions are well-informed and necessary.

Efficient inventory management enhances lab productivity and reduces costs. Managing inventory is essential for the smooth operation of any laboratory, regardless of its size. It can be challenging to monitor consumable supplies, reagents, lab equipment, and instruments. However, implementing efficient inventory management practices can greatly improve productivity and reduce costs. By using simple and creative strategies, you can maximize your lab budget and enhance overall efficiency.

This research focuses on assessing the inventory, handling practices, and management practices of the Science Laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus. The study aims to evaluate the availability and condition of lab equipment, assess the handling practices related to safety measures, and examine the management practices implemented in the laboratory.

The research methodology includes conducting an inventory assessment of the lab equipment, categorizing them into common equipment for safety purposes, basic apparatus, glassware apparatus used for measuring, glassware apparatus not used for measuring, and common equipment for heating. The assessment will provide insights into the adequacy and functionality of the lab equipment.

Furthermore, the study will assess the handling practices in terms of personal protective equipment and clothing, availability of emergency equipment, and the level of housekeeping in the laboratory. This assessment will help identify areas for improvement in ensuring a safe and secure laboratory environment.

Lastly, the research will evaluate the management practices in the laboratory, including the calibration and repair of equipment, checking of new and used laboratory equipment, and the cleaning and organization of equipment and countertops. This assessment will shed light on the effectiveness of current management practices and identify areas for enhancement.

The findings of this research will be the basis for formulating an action plan, that provide valuable information for improving the Science Laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus. The results will guide the implementation of necessary measures to enhance the inventory, handling practices, and management practices in the laboratory. It is expected that the research outcomes will contribute to the overall improvement of the laboratory's functionality, safety, and efficiency.

Research Questions

This study aims to analyze the inventory, handling and management practices of Science Laboratory of Mindoro State University (MinSU). Bongabong Campus
Specific Questions:

1. What is Inventory assessment of science laboratory of MinSU Bongabong Campus in terms of:
 - 1.1 Common Lab Equipment
 - 1.2 Glassware- Used For Measurement
 - 1.3 Equipment Often Used In Titrations
 - 1.4 Basic Laboratory Equipment
2. What is the extent of satisfaction of the respondents in Handling practices assessment of Science Laboratory of MinSU Bongabong Campus in terms of:
 - 2.1 personal protective equipment and clothing,
 - 2.2 emergency equipment, and
 - 2.3 housekeeping
3. What is the extent of satisfaction of the respondents in Management Practices assessment of Science Laboratory of MinSU Bongabong Campus in terms of:
 - 3.1 calibration of laboratory equipment
 - 3.2 repairing of Laboratory equipment
 - 3.3 checking of new and used laboratory equipment
4. What specific Action Plan could be proposed based on the findings?

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research design used to answer the specific research questions as well as the research setting, participants, sampling, and the detailed data gathering procedures, and analysis, and ethical considerations.

Research Design. The research used the descriptive method to conduct this study. Descriptive research employed to describe the status of the laboratory materials, apparatus and equipment in Science Laboratory through inventory assessment. It is also used in describing the Handling practices and Management Practices of Science Laboratory of MinSU Bongabong Campus.

Research Participants and Sampling. Sixty Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Science took part in the study. These number of respondents were selected from the three year level with a total population of 85 students, There were 20 student from second, third, and fourth year respectively and eight faculty members teaching science involved as respondents with a total number 68.

Data Collection. A written request duly noted by the Program Chair (PC) to conduct a study and to distribute the questionnaire to the students and faculty respondents was sent to the Campus Executive Director (CED) for approval. Upon approval the questionnaire was distributed personally to the respondents. Retrieval of the questionnaire was made after one day. The data gathered were tabulated, analyzed and interpreted.

Instruments. To gather the data from respondents, a self-made questionnaire was used as instrument. The questionnaire focused on the handling practices and management practices of science laboratory of MinSU Bongabong Campus. Meanwhile, another source of data was the inventory records of the laboratory equipment from the supply office.

Data Analysis. The quantitative data gathered were treated using Descriptive Statistics such as mean. On the other hand, the inventory records from the Supply Office were also used to described the status of the different science laboratory apparatus and equipment.

RESULTS

This section presents the results of the data analysis done by the researchers. The results were presented in a way that answers the research questions which were previously stated.

Table 1. Inventory assessment of science laboratory of MinSU Bongabong Campus

Common Lab Equipment	Quantity	Good Condition (GC)	Not Good Condition (NGC)	None (N)
Fire extinguisher		/		
Safety goggles		/		
Safety gloves		/		
Lab coats/gown		/		
First aid kit				/
Emergency shower				/
Erlenmeyer Flask		/		
Beaker		/		
Test Tube		/		
Vial With Cap				/

Glassware- Used For Measurement				
1. Volumetric Flask			/	
2. Graduated Cylinder		/		

3. Pipet			/	
4. Buret			/	
Equipment Often Used In Titrations				
1. Ring Stand			/	
2. Buret Clamp			/	
3. Utility Clamp			/	

Basic Laboratory Equipment				
1. Funnel		/		
2. Watch Glass			/	
3. Crucible Tongs				/
4. Glass Stir Bar			/	
5. Centrifuge			/	
6. Bunsen Burner			/	
7. Magnetic Stir Bar			/	
8. Disposable Pipet				/
9. Wash Bottle				/
10. Pipet Bulb				/
11. Desiccator			/	

Magnifying Instrument				
Magnifying glass		/		
Compound Microscope		/		
Electronic Microscope			/	
	Weighing Balance			
Gram Balance Scale			/	
Analytical Weighing Balance		/		
Electronic Weighing Balance			/	

Legend for Inventory Process **Good Condition (GC)** **Not Good Condition (NGC)** **None (N)**

Table 1 shows the inventory assessment of science laboratory of MinSU Bongabong Campus.

Based on the inventory of the science laboratory equipment and materials, it appears that some items were not present, and some were not functioning properly. Additionally, only a few items were found to be in working condition.

Part II. The handling practices assessment of the Science Laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus in terms of;

Table 2. Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) and Clothing

Indicator	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Laboratory personnel/instructor/students consistently wear the appropriate PPE (e.g., lab coats, gloves, safety goggles) during all laboratory activities	2.62	2.5	Often
2. Laboratory personnel/instructor provided with proper training on the correct usage and disposal of PPE	2.54	4	Often
3. there is a designated area or facilities for storing and changing into/out of PPE within the laboratory	2.62	2.5	Often

4. There is a clear policy or guideline in place regarding the use of PPE in the laboratory	2.68	1	Often
5. Regular inspections or assessments conducted to ensure compliance with PPE usage among laboratory personnel and instructor	2.47	5	Often
Overall Mean	2.79		Often

Table 2 presents the mean on handling practices assessment of the Science Laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus in terms of PPE and clothing. As seen in the table, item 4, there is a clear policy or guideline in place regarding the use of PPE in the laboratory have mean score of 2.68, ranked 1st and with often as verbal description. This implies that a clear policy regarding the use of PPE is essential to properly guided the laboratory users.

It can also be observed from the table that regular inspections or assessments conducted to ensure compliance with PPE usage among laboratory personnel and instructor got a mean score of 2.47, ranked last with often as verbal description. The results revealed that regular inspections or assessments must be conducted for meaningful practices.

Table 3. Emergency Equipment

Indicator	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Emergency equipment, such as fire extinguishers, readily accessible and properly maintained within the laboratory	2.78	2	Often
2. There is a clear procedure or protocol in place for using emergency equipment in case of an emergency situation	2.65	3	Often
3. Laboratory personnel/instructor trained on the proper usage of emergency equipment, such as fire extinguishers or emergency eyewash stations	2.59	5	Often
4. Emergency equipment regularly inspected and tested to ensure they are in good working condition	2.90	1	Often

5. Emergency equipment clearly labeled and their locations prominently displayed within the laboratory	2.62	4	Often
Overall Mean	2.71		often

Table 3 presents the mean on handling practices assessment of the Science Laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus in terms of emergency equipment. Emergency equipment regularly inspected and tested to ensure they are in good working condition ranked 1st, described as often which gained mean value of 2.90. Regular inspections and tests on emergency equipment indicate a proactive approach to maintenance and safety.

On the other hand, item number 3 received the mean score of 2.59 with verbal description of often and ranked last. However, there is room for improvement in terms of training laboratory personnel and instructors on the proper usage of emergency equipment.

The overall mean is 2.71 with verbal description of often was achieved. According to Becerik-Gerber et al., (2012) emergency supplies should focus on ensuring ongoing readiness and safety in crisis situations. To analyze the overall results, it can be noted that handling practices in terms of emergency equipment should give attention to ensure continuous preparedness and safety in emergency situations.

Table 4. Housekeeping

Indicator	Mean	Rank	Description
1. The laboratory is maintained in terms of cleanliness and tidiness	2.62	2	Often
2. The laboratory personnel trained on proper housekeeping practices, such as cleaning spills and maintaining a clutter-free workspace	2.54	3	Often
3. There are designated areas or containers for waste disposal within the laboratory	2.21	4	Often
4. The chemicals and hazardous materials properly stored and labeled in the laboratory	2.65	1	Often
5. The laboratory countertops and workspaces are cleaned and sanitized	2.09	5	Rarely
Overall Mean	2.42		Rarely

Table 3 presents the mean on handling practices assessment of the Science Laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus in terms of housekeeping.

As seen in the table, item 4, the chemicals and hazardous materials properly stored and labeled in the laboratory have mean score of 2.65 ranked 1st and with often as verbal description. The item implies that the chemical and hazardous materials must properly stored and labeled in the laboratory to avoid any unnecessary incidents.

It can also be observed from the table that the laboratory countertop and workspace are cleaned and sanitized got a mean score of 2.09, ranked last with rarely as verbal interpretation. The result revealed that the laboratory should prioritize regular cleaning and sanitization to ensure a safe and healthy working environment

However, the overall mean is 2.42 with verbal description of rarely. The results implies that laboratory housekeeping needed more attention of cleaning and sanitation to maintain quality services of the laboratory. Cleaning and sanitation in the lab needed to be prioritized in order to maintain the level of quality services provided by the facility (Housekeeping, 2021).

Table 5. Summary of the mean on the handling practices assessment of the Science Laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus

Indicator	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) and Clothing	2.79	1	Often
2. Emergency Equipment	2.71	2	Often
3. Housekeeping	2.42	3	Rarely
Overall Mean	2.64		Often

Table 5 the presents summary of the mean on the handling practices assessment of the Science Laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus.

The result shown in the table implies that participants were generally dissatisfied with the variable housekeeping, as it obtained the lowest mean score of 2.42 and was ranked three.

Despite receiving often verbal descriptions, both Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) and Clothing, as well as Emergency Equipment, obtained relatively low mean scores of 2.79 and 2.71 respectively. This suggests that participants were not fully satisfied with these variables. The verbal descriptions often may have been insufficient in addressing any concerns or difficulties related to the use or availability of PPE and Clothing, as well as Emergency Equipment. The overall mean score of 2.64, with a verbal description of often, indicates a generally low level of satisfaction across all variables.

Based on these results, it is evident that there are areas for improvement in terms of housekeeping, as well as the provision and understanding of Personal Protective

Equipment (PPE) and Clothing, and Emergency Equipment. Emergency equipment, such as fire extinguishers, eyewash stations, and emergency showers, plays a critical role in ensuring the safety of personnel and mitigating potential hazards in a laboratory and should be regularly inspected, maintained, and easily accessible to effectively respond to any emergency situation (Kronick et al., 2015).

Part III: The management practices assessment of the Science Laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus in terms of:

Table 6. Calibration of Laboratory Equipment

Indicator	Mean	Rank	Description
1. There is a documented calibration schedule for laboratory equipment in place	3.46	3	Often
2. There are trained and qualified personnel responsible for conducting equipment calibration	1.40	4	Never
3. The calibration records maintained and updated for each laboratory equipment	3.39	1	Often
4. The calibration results reviewed and acted upon in a timely manner	3.32	5	Often
5. There are procedures in place for addressing any deviations or issues identified during equipment calibration	3.47	2	Often
Overall Mean	3.03		Often

Table 6 portrays the mean on management practices assessment of the science laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus in terms of calibration of laboratory equipment.

The table described that item 3 the calibration records maintained and updated for each laboratory equipment ranked 1st with the mean value 3.39 with often verbal description. This result asserts that maintaining and updating calibration record of the laboratory equipment manifest a systematic approach in keeping records.

Likewise, item 4, the calibration results reviewed and acted upon in a timely manner have mean value of 3.32, ranked last have often verbal description. This manifest that commitment to review calibration results is commendable.

Generally, table 6 has an overall mean of 3.03 with verbal description of often. The

results implies that the laboratory should continue to prioritize equipment calibration and invest in training personnel to enhance their expertise in this area. This result is supported by Madu (2012) that laboratory should keep placing a high priority on equipment calibration and spend money on staff training to increase their knowledge in this area.

Table 7. Repairing of laboratory equipment

Indicator	Mean	Rank	Description
1. There is a designated process or system in place for reporting and documenting equipment issues or malfunctions	3.56	2	Always
2. There is a trained and qualified personnel responsible for conducting equipment repairs	3.53	3	Always
3. There are established timelines or response times for addressing equipment repairs	3.59	1	Always
4. The equipment repair records maintained and updated for each repair conducted	2.65	4	Often
5. There are procedures in place for prioritizing and scheduling equipment repairs based on urgency and impact on laboratory operations	2.59	5	Often
Overall Mean	3.18		Often

Table 7 present the mean on managing practicess assessment in terms of repairing of laboratory equipment.

Item 3, there are established timelines or response times for addressing equipment repairs ranked 1st as always which gained 3.59. The result implies that timeline or response timeline indicate a structured and timely approached to equipment repairs.

On the other hand, the item 5, there are procedures in place for prioritizing and scheduling equipment repairs based on urgency and impact on laboratory operation, received the mean score of 2.59 with verbal description of often and ranked last. The results shows that there is a need for prioritizing and scheduling equipment repairs based on urgency and impact.

Furthermore, the table also shows an overall mean of 3.18 with a verbal description of often. The results shows an evident that the laboratory should continue to prioritize equipment maintenance and repairs to minimize downtime and ensure smooth laboratory operations. As an evidence to this statement Bento and Fontes (2015), mentioned that the laboratory should keep giving equipment maintenance and repairs top priority in order

to minimize downtime and ensure effective laboratory operations.

Table 8. Checking New and Used Laboratory Equipment

Indicator	Mean	Rank	Description
1. There is a documented process in place for checking new laboratory equipment before it is put into use	3.56	4	Always
2. The trained and qualified personnel are responsible for conducting checks on new laboratory equipment	3.59	2	Always
3. There are established criteria or standards for checking the functionality and safety of new laboratory equipment	3.60	1	Always
4. There is a process in place for checking and assessing the condition of used laboratory equipment before it is used or acquired	3.57	3	Always
5. There are criteria or standards for evaluating the condition and functionality of used laboratory equipment	3.51	5	Always
Overall Mean	3.57		Always

Table 8 presents the mean on the management practices assessment of the Science Laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus Checking in terms of New and Used Laboratory Equipment.

As show in the table, item 3, there are established criteria or standards for checking the functionality and safety of new laboratory equipment received 3.60 mean score, ranked 1st and verbal description of always. This implies that there is systematic and thorough approach to equipment checks.

Meanwhile, item 5, there are criteria or standards for evaluating the condition and functionality of used laboratory equipment received the 3.51 mean score, which ranked last and with always verbal description. The results manifest that in the laboratory should consider the evaluation of the condition and functionality of the used laboratory equipment to minimize the risk of using faulty and unsafe equipment.

Finally, the table shows the overall mean score of 3.57, the always verbal description. The result implies that the laboratory should continue to prioritize equipment

checks to ensure the quality and reliability of the equipment used in laboratory operations. According to Asia (2011) that to ensure the quality and dependability of the equipment used in laboratory operations, laboratories should continue to prioritize equipment checks.

Table 9. Summary of the mean on the management practices assessment of the Science Laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus

Indicator	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Calibration of Laboratory Equipment	3.03	3	Often
2. Repairing of laboratory equipment	3.18	2	Often
3. Checking New and Used Laboratory Equipment	3.57	1	always
Overall Mean	3.26		Often

Table 9 shows summary of the mean on the management practices assessment of the Science Laboratory at MinSU Bongabong Campus

The results showed in the table is the summary of the mean responses of the participants which generally implied that they more satisfied with the indicator checking new and used laboratory equipment, which received the highest mean score of 3.57 and was ranked as one. The provision of a verbal description always seems to have implied a significant role in improving this aspect. On the other hand, the variable of repairing laboratory equipment received a slightly lower mean score of 3.18 and was ranked as two.

The variable calibration of laboratory equipment received the lowest mean score of 3.03 and was ranked as three. This suggests that participants were relatively less satisfied with this variable. Despite the verbal description often, it may not have been sufficient to adequately address any concerns or difficulties associated with the calibration process of the laboratory equipment. Overall, the mean score of 3.26, with a verbal description of often, indicates a moderate level of satisfaction across all variables.

What specific SciLab Training-Workshop could be proposed based on the findings?

The Proposed Action Plan

Title: Enhancing Science Laboratory Inventory, Handling Practices, and Management Practices Action Plan

Activity	Responsible Parties	Timeline	Resources Required
Assess current inventory system	Laboratory Personnel	Week 1	Inventory records, observation checklist
Update inventory records	Inventory Team	Week 2	Digital inventory management software, labeling materials
Conduct a thorough inventory audit	Inventory Team	Week 3	Physical inventory count, disposal guidelines
Implement a standardized labeling system	Lab Personnel, Inventory Team	Week 4	Labeling materials, labeling guidelines
Establish storage guidelines	Lab Personnel, electrician	Week 5	Storage guidelines, segregation materials
Train staff on handling procedures	Lab Personnel, Training Department	Week 6	Training materials, PPE, handling protocols
Develop safety protocols	Lab Personnel, Maintenance Officer	Week 7	SOP templates, safety guidelines
Implement regular safety inspections	Electrician and Maintenance Officer	Week 8	Implement regular safety inspections
Conduct staff training on safety practices	Lab Personnel, Training Department	Week 9	Training materials, safety equipment
Monitor and Establish a maintenance schedule	Lab Personnel, Maintenance Team	Week 10	Maintenance schedule, equipment checklist
Evaluate and adapt	Lab Personnel , Stakeholders	Ongoing	Feedback forms, improvement plan

DISCUSSION

On table 1, shows several implications. Firstly, the absence of certain equipment means that students and researchers may not have access to all the necessary tools for conducting experiments or carrying out their work effectively. This can hinder their progress and limit the scope of their scientific investigations. According to the study of Cossa, et.al (2015), laboratory equipment and learning materials are in short supply due to the lack of funds. In connection to the problem of scarcity of laboratory materials the university must identify the most critical items needed for hands-on science activities and prioritize their acquisition. Focus on acquiring equipment and materials that are necessary for fundamental experiments and activities that align with the curriculum.

Secondly, the presence of non-functioning equipment poses a challenge as it may lead to inaccurate results or unreliable data. This can negatively impact the quality of research and experimentation conducted in the laboratory. Always remember that science is an experimental discipline, laboratory becomes an essential part in enhancing students' scientific skills (Suleiman, 2013). This will not be materialized if the laboratory materials are not in good condition or not functioning.

Lastly, the limited number of functioning items can result in a bottleneck, where multiple individuals or groups have to share the available equipment. This can lead to delays, decreased productivity, and potential conflicts over resource allocation. According to Ngozi & Halima (2015) inadequate laboratory facilities hinder effective teaching and learning and may contribute to the poor performance of students.

These are the reason why university and other educational institution must address the inadequacy of laboratory materials to avoid delay and hinder laboratory works and activities. A thorough assessment of the inventory should be conducted to identify missing items and repair or replace non-functioning equipment. Adequate funding and resources should be allocated to ensure that the laboratory is well-equipped and maintained to support scientific research and educational activities effectively.

Meanwhile on table 2, the results manifest that the laboratory has a slightly good level of compliance with PPE usage. However, there may be room for improvement, particularly in providing more comprehensive training on PPE usage and disposal and conducting more frequent inspections or assessments to ensure ongoing compliance. The results is supported with Ranney et al.,(2020) that laboratory must provide with Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), includes items like gloves, goggles, lab coats, and respirators, should be worn correctly and consistently to reduce the risk of exposure to chemicals, biological agents, or physical hazards, is crucial in a laboratory setting to safeguard individuals from potential hazards and ensure their safety.

However, on table 3 got an overall mean is 2.71 with verbal description of often was achieved. According to Becerik-Gerber et al., (2012) emergency supplies should focus on ensuring ongoing readiness and safety in crisis situations. To analyze the overall results, it can be noted that handling practices in terms of emergency equipment should give attention to ensure continuous preparedness and safety in emergency situations.

On table 4, the results implies that laboratory housekeeping needed more attention

of cleaning and sanitation to maintain quality services of the laboratory. Cleaning and sanitation in the lab needed to be prioritized in order to maintain the level of quality services provided by the facility (Housekeeping, 2021).

Based from the result on table 5, it is evident that there are areas for improvement in terms of housekeeping, as well as the provision and understanding of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) and Clothing, and Emergency Equipment. Emergency equipment, such as fire extinguishers, eyewash stations, and emergency showers, plays a critical role in ensuring the safety of personnel and mitigating potential hazards in a laboratory and should be regularly inspected, maintained, and easily accessible to effectively respond to any emergency situation (Kronick et al., 2015).

However, table 6 has an overall mean of 3.03 with verbal description of often. The results implies that the laboratory should continue to prioritize equipment calibration and invest in training personnel to enhance their expertise in this area. This result supported by Madu (2012) that laboratory should keep placing a high priority on equipment calibration and spend money on staff training to increase their knowledge in this area.

Furthermore, the table 7 shows an overall mean of 3.18 with a verbal description of often. The results shows an evident that the laboratory should continue to prioritize equipment maintenance and repairs to minimize downtime and ensure smooth laboratory operations. As an evidence to this statement Bento and Fontes (2015), mentioned that the laboratory should keep giving equipment maintenance and repairs top priority in order to minimize downtime and ensure effective laboratory operations.

Looking on the table 8, it shows the overall mean score of 3.57, the always verbal description. The result implies that the laboratory should continue to prioritize equipment checks to ensure the quality and reliability of the equipment used in laboratory operations. According to Asia (2011) that to ensure the quality and dependability of the equipment used in laboratory operations, laboratories should continue to prioritize equipment checks.

Table 8 states that timely repairs help to reduce downtime, ensure accurate results, and prolong the lifespan of equipment, enabling uninterrupted scientific research and experimentation. Maintaining the functionality and dependability of laboratory equipment is crucial for keeping scientific instruments reliable and functional (De Moraes Ramos et al., 2017). Calibration of science laboratory equipment is a critical process that ensures reliable and consistent results, enabling researchers and students to trust the data obtained from their experiments. It involves ensuring the accuracy and precision of measurement instruments by comparing their readings to known standards (WHO, 2011).

The results also indicates a moderate level of satisfaction across all variables. This suggests that the verbal descriptions often were generally helpful in facilitating understanding and satisfaction, but there may be room for improvement in particular to the said variables.

Conclusions

1. From the findings there are several issues with the science laboratory equipment and materials, including missing items, non-functioning equipment, and a limited number of functioning items.
2. The respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the variables of housekeeping, Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) and Clothing, and Emergency Equipment.
3. The participants were most satisfied with the indicator of checking new and used laboratory equipment, while repairing laboratory equipment received a slightly lower level of satisfaction.

Recommendations

1. The university may conduct a thorough assessment of the inventory to identify missing items and repair or replace non-functioning equipment. Adequate funding should be allocated to ensure the laboratory is well-equipped and maintained.
2. The institution should emphasize the important to improve the provision and understanding of housekeeping, PPE and Clothing, and Emergency Equipment. This can be achieved through regular training and orientation on proper use and availability of PPE and Clothing, as well as ensuring cleanliness and organization in the laboratory for better housekeeping.
3. The university should improve the repair process by addressing any delays or difficulties. This can be done by implementing a system for timely repairs, providing clear communication and updates to participants on the status of repairs, and addressing any concerns or difficulties related to the repair process.
4. The university should adopt the proposed **Enhancing Science Laboratory Inventory, Handling Practices, and Management Practices Action Plan**

Compliance With Ethical Standards

Throughout the conduct of the study, research ethics were considered by the researcher. Aside from the permission secured from the CED, the proposal was presented to the institutional review committee to make sure it would not violate any research ethics and that it would serve its purpose. Voluntary participation was observed right during sampling. The respondents were asked to sign the informed consent. They are assured of the confidentiality, anonymity of their identities and their responses, and were informed of their right to withdraw their participation in the study.

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